

SOCIAL ASPECTS OF PREPARING CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL NEEDS FOR FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS (DEVELOPING A FAMILIST WORLD VIEW)

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Abstract: The article examines the social aspects of preparing children with disabilities for future family relationships. Special attention is given to the role of family, educational institutions, and social organizations in shaping concepts of family, developing communication skills, and fostering personal self-determination.

Keywords: children with disabilities, preparation for family life, socialization, social pedagogy, family relationships.

In our country, attention has always been paid to the equal attention of all children, to their preparation for society, adult life and family. In particular, the attention paid to the education of children with special needs is also growing significantly. Efforts are being made to fully integrate them into society, to make them independent and self-sufficient members of society. Great attention is paid to the education of such children, and from school age they are taught self-service skills, to prepare them for adult life, to explain the rules of interacting with people, and to teach them moral concepts.

Preparation for family life is also one of the important stages of a person's socialization. For children in need of special assistance, this process has its own characteristics due to physical and psycho-emotional limitations, as well as social barriers such as stereotypes and misperceptions in society. In the context of the development of inclusive education and increasing attention to issues of equality, it is of urgent importance to study the mechanisms of preparing such children for future family life. According to sociologist A. Abduganiyev, family competence is an integrated set of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and emotional potential necessary for a person to perform specific tasks within the family system, effectively organize family communication and develop mechanisms of mutual support. This approach is based on a deep analysis of roles, tasks and social relations in the family system.

The urgency of the problem is that, despite the active development of socialization processes for people with disabilities, the issues of their future family life have not been sufficiently studied. The perception that marriage, parenthood, and full-fledged partnership are the privilege of only "healthy" people still persists in the minds of society. Such views, in turn, prevent the formation of stable positive ideas about the possibility of children with special needs to build their own families. The thinking activity of children with special needs was analyzed in the scientific works of such scientists as L.I. Solntseva, O.E. Mukhordova, N.V. Gorodilova, and it became clear that the ideas of these children about the future family differ from the ideas of their peers. Like all people, this category of individuals strive to build a strong family. By satisfying this need, the chances of successful socialization of adolescents with disabilities increase (V.I. Lubovsky[2], L.I. Solntseva[1], V.V. Tkacheva[6], L.M. Shipitsina[8]). An analysis of the studied psychological and pedagogical literature has shown that the personal characteristics of adolescents in need of special assistance differ

significantly from those of normally developing adolescents. This is expressed in emotional imbalance, inability to control their actions with sufficient willpower, and shortcomings in self-awareness and self-acceptance. However, in some adolescents, under the influence of a favorable social environment, some personal indicators improve. This allows us to assume that the period of adolescence is more favorable for conducting sexual education work. E.A. Denisova's research shows that in adolescence, children with special needs show increased attention to their appearance, an increased interest in issues of gender, sexuality, and sexuality, a new quality of orientation to the future and an assessment of marital and family relationships appears. It is at this age that high school students with mental retardation develop psychological readiness to form the right relationships with friends, love, and family.

Currently, many support programs for the integration of children with special needs into society are focused on socialization, vocational guidance or medical rehabilitation, while emotional, communication and family-domestic preparation are somewhat neglected. If this attitude continues, that is, if the child is not actively involved in school and extracurricular life, the child with disabilities may face social isolation in the future, which complicates both his emotional development and his vision of a possible family role.

In her scientific research, M.U. Khamidova has obtained information that the personal development of children with special needs depends on the attitude of their parents towards their child and the ways and methods they choose to raise and develop him. Ultimately, the way of life in the family changes as a result of their correct acceptance of their children or vice versa, and this situation also affects the child. S.Turgunbayev, in his scientific work, stated that by developing interpersonal relationships in the family, teaching social skills, including behavior, etiquette and morals, and introducing the etiquette of communicating with family members, the child's socialization occurs not only with family members, but also with other people in society.

Instead of a recommendation, it can be said that, first of all, when educating a child, a teacher should create opportunities for children in educational institutions - especially in the inclusive education system - to form communication skills, participation in collective activities, decision-making and mutual assistance. All this will help the child prepare for future family partnerships. Social educators, psychologists, tutors can include elements of preparation for family life in individual educational areas, such as discussing the topics of family, love, responsibility, developing conflict resolution skills, forming positive self-esteem, role-playing games and theatrical exercises. These practices can be especially effective if they are adapted to the characteristics of a particular child and carried out in collaboration with parents.

Also, in preparing a child for adult life, not only the educational institution, but also the family itself plays a central role in the socialization of the child. In many cases, parents themselves do not believe that their child will be able to marry and develop as a parent in the future. This is due to both their anxiety and insufficient awareness of the child's capabilities. It is necessary to explain to parents the importance of preparing the child for independent life, including possible family relationships. Providing psychological counseling when working with families, inviting them to participate in parenting clubs, and teaching methods of upbringing aimed at independence and cooperation are another important task for the educator.

In addition, it is necessary to develop various programs to prepare children with special needs for adult and family life. Through these support programs, various projects can be implemented (organizing special courses and trainings, involving mentors in classes - including people with disabilities who have successful family life experience, organizing inclusive camps). Such various organizational activities help to form social ties, broaden the worldview and create an experience of positive interactions based on respect, trust and acceptance.

In conclusion, preparing children with special needs for family life is an important and multifaceted process, requiring an interdisciplinary approach and cooperation. In this, it is important not only to develop practical skills, but also to form a vision of oneself as a full-fledged participant in family relations. Such a result can be achieved quickly only through active cooperation between the family, school and social services.

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